

Data Processing

ARCFISH 1st General Assembly

KD Blue Insight

Introducing the

Task Orchestrator

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~~Task Orchestrator~~

Analytics Workflow Engine (AWE)

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Cloud vs. local

- Local development
- Run from anywhere

Analytics Workflow Engine (AWE)

Cloud vs. local

```
Python 3.12.3 (main, Sep 5 2024, 10:52:02) [GCC 11.4.0] on linux
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> import numpy
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "<stdin>", line 1, in <module>
ModuleNotFoundError: No module named 'numpy'
>>> |
```


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Cloud vs. local

```
Anaconda Prompt (ANACONDA3)
The system cannot find the path specified.
The system cannot find the path specified.
The system cannot find the file C:\Users\p#an\AppData\Local\Temp\conda-9411-18271.tmp.
The system cannot find the path specified.

C:\Users\p#an!>python -m pip install pymongo
C:\Users\p#an!\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python36\python.exe: No module named pip

C:\Users\p#an!>_
```


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Cloud vs. local

- Local development
- Run from anywhere
- Deterministic runtime

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Containerization

«Great! My code works in Jupyter Notebooks»

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Containerization

«I have this Matlab code»

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Containerization

«Wow, my C++ code compiles on my machine!»

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Containerization

«But does it work on my machine?»

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Containerization

- Same Python version?
- Same packages? No conflicts?
- Different OS behavior – typically Tensorflow, PyTorch etc.
- Cue containerization

Simply put, we package **all dependencies and configurations** to ensure a **consistent and reproducible** environment across **different systems**.

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What is that whale doing here?

And why the whale? Well, this is Docker, the most widely used containerization platform! Alternatives are Kubernetes (runs Docker Containers), Podman and Linux containers (LXC)

Simply put, we package **all dependencies and configurations** to ensure a **consistent and reproducible** environment across **different systems**.

Analytics Workflow Engine (AWE)

How to use Docker?

With a single **dockerfile** – we can ensure deterministic behavior across all systems

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But I use GitHub, not Docker

GitHub

With a single **dockerfile** – we can ensure deterministic behavior across all systems

Analytics Workflow Engine (AWE)

Containerization

Ready for **production**?

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Containerization

Ready for **production**?

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Containerization

With Docker, we have a way to run all our code deterministically on all machines

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Containerization

But what about
non-local runs?

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From local collection to Blue Insight

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Questions so far?